

Integrated Education at Jazan University: Budding Hope for Employability

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Abstract—Experience is what makes a man perfect. Though we tend to learn many a different things in life through practice still we need to go an extra mile to gain experience which would be profitable only when it is integrated with regular practice. A clear phenomenal idea is that every teacher is a learner.

The centralized idea of this paper would focus on the integrated practices carried out among the students of Jizan University which enhances learning through experiences. Integrated practices like student-directed activities, balanced curriculum, phonological based activities and use of consistent language would enlarge the vision and mission of students to earn experience through learning. Students who receive explicit instruction and guidance could practice the skills and strategies through student-directed activities such as peer tutoring and cooperative learning. The second effective practice is to use consistent language. Consistent language provides students a model for talking about the new concepts which also enables them to communicate without hindrances. Phonological awareness is an important early reading skill for all students. Students generally have phonemic awareness in their home language can often transfer that knowledge to a second language. And also a balanced curriculum requires instruction in all the elements of reading. Reading is the most effective skill when both basic and higher-order skills are included on a daily basis. Computer based reading and listening skills will empower students to understand language in a better way. English language learners can benefit from sound reading instruction even before they are fully proficient in English as long as the instruction is comprehensible. Thus, if students have to be well equipped in learning they should foreground themselves in various integrated practices through multifarious experience for which teachers are moderators and trainers. This type of learning prepares the students for a constantly changing society which helps them to meet the competitive world around them for better employability fulfilling the vision and mission of the institution.

Keywords—Consistent language, employability, phonological awareness, balanced curriculum.

I. INTRODUCTION

TECHNOLOGY-ENHANCED learning is not a new concept. Students at Jizan University enter a classroom that looks like any other, except that a projection system and video screen have been installed. This is an example of one of the creative ways faculty members at Jazan are using technology to enhance their students' learning. Across the University, faculty is using technology to help students master their subjects. They are developing their own skills while making students comfortable with the technology that will help them to be successful after leaving the University. As

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they introduce more and more technology into the classroom, faculty is finding it raises the quality of class discussion and involves students much more deeply in their own education. "Achievement of success thus requires that faculty take the core of knowledge that is vital to us and integrate it with the new learning modes. Our new student learners are motivated to acquire information [2], [3], [6]". There will a focus and reflection on what integrated education is and how it helps, complements and enhances employability would be discussed and approaches to addressing and embedding integrated education would be dealt anonymously.

II. TEACHER AND INTEGRATED EDUCATION

Teachers teach methods and courses in a classroom, integrating traditional lecture with demonstration projects using the methods they are teaching. Teachers guide the students in the preparation of multi-media classroom presentations including clips from the Internet, video, audio, and news archive footage. What Technology Brings to the Classroom? What these faculty members have in common and what they share with many others across the campus is a commitment to exploring the opportunities technology offers for improving the quality of classroom instruction. Incorporating computers into class discussion can also make extremely difficult courses much easier for students to grasp.

"I have been part of a group that has been developing innovative responses to the current challenges. This response consists of integrating three components: deep learning goals, new pedagogies, and technology. The result will be more radical change in the next five years than has occurred in the past 50 years [11]."

There is no book that is perfect, that really is appropriate, for any class. There is either book that tends to be too easy or too hard or just not broad enough in scope. Thus, books are replaced by technology for better understanding and interest. Technology changes Teaching, not Teachers while the faculty members believe that technology has great power to influence their teaching, no one feels it fundamentally changes them as teachers.

Technology enhances the students' learning, particularly when students use the technology directly. Students should be exposed to do everything virtually. In this way they will have a lot to figure out about group process, what things are done best face to face, what things are done best asynchronously, what things are done best in an anonymous chat room. And they figure it out. This would mean much more powerful than the teacher sitting up there saying what to be done. Technology can also improve the dynamics between teachers

and students, often leading to enhanced learning. Management can see us doing a lot of work to further improve the student's education and definitely, there will be an appreciation factor that ultimately contributes to our motivation. According to Stephen Kemmis and Robin Mc. Taggret, "Focusing on practices in a concrete and specific way makes them accessible reflection, discussion, and reconstruction as products of past circumstances that are capable of being modified in and for present and future circumstances [8]."

Educators have integrated technology into their instruction for as long as there have been classrooms. Teachers also enhance student's usage of consistent language for effective communication skills. Whether it is through textbooks made possible through the invention of the printing press, an overhead projector, a film strip, or an online simulation, teachers have always looked toward technology to provide students with higher quality learning experiences. Integrated education aims to equip students with a set of capabilities which they can apply in any context they choose in. Having the attitude, ability and take up opportunities and create a suitable environment to make the most of them.

III. INTEGRATED LEARNING AND EMPLOYABILITY: EMBEDDING EMPLOYABILITY INTO THE CURRICULUM

Process of equipping students with enhanced capacity to generate ideas and skills is through employability. To make it happen with attributes and capacities and skills need a special protocol for students to move to a higher grade in achieving what they really want in their life.

"Much that has taken place in higher education over the years has supported the promotion of employability – and this is a continuing feature of the higher education landscape. There is a need to step back from day-to-day concerns to identify ways in which employability might be further enhanced without prejudicing the subject-specific dimension of learning [12]." Thus proves that higher education has always supported employability. However, innovations in this context are obviously needed for a better achiever to hold on to records. Adaptive learning is changing what it means to educate students in the 21st century. New technologies are enhancing our understanding of how students learn and providing instructors the ability to customize course materials and create personalized learning experiences tailored to students' individual needs and thereby enabling student's employability. Thus, assimilation with integrated learning helps students in solving, decision making and also to be creative and innovative. Apart from these abilities it also assists students for a better leadership with interpersonal skills and confidence with perseverance. Thus, it also boosts up the communicative skills with implementing ideas and resilience. Phonological awareness still is an add-on advantage to a better reading and understanding which would equip the learners in better understanding. Each and everything finally contributes for a suitable employment.

As technology and instructional methods evolve, so do students' expectations for a technology-driven learning experience increases. Personal attributes, knowledge, skill

enables students to gain employment and to achieve the goal in their career. Emerging online learning models encourage students to be more active participants in their own learning - allowing them to not just be content consumers, but content creators as well. As digital natives, students want to attend a university that effectively integrates the latest technologies and teaching methods into their education.

Student's attributes for better employability through integrated learning would entitle them for a better tomorrow. All they need is to incorporate and initialize themselves with attributes such as

1. Effective communication,
2. Confidence,
3. Independent,
4. Resourceful,
5. Reflective,
6. Responsible,
7. Adaptable,
8. Critical thinking.

"Technological developments in sound and video will enable students to use a range of senses for representing their experiences while they access resources that they discover and participate in new networks that offer learning opportunities [4]." Technology should be used in service to specific learning goals you have for your students. That is every instructor can use technology to enhance their teaching in uniquely effective ways. Throughout the Jazan University campus, innovative faculty are exploring new and interesting ways to integrate technology into their curriculum. Whether we want to put our course online, make better use of experiment with other forms of technology-enhanced active learning, we have chosen and organized these resources to help guide the students in a different way. Technology brings challenges which when introduced in a class enables students incorporate new technology into learning.

Moving forward with technology as Jazan University moves towards an increasingly coordinated approach to the use of technology, several efforts are underway at to determine just how technology can be used to enhance learning. Among is several priorities is research into the value of technology, such as web-based education for teaching nursing and pharmacy students.

The academic institutions should develop a new curriculum in nursing one that utilizes fundamental principles of learning science and that it is driven by technology, web based technology, simulations, slides, interactive systems, and tutoring and homework systems to encourage students to individuality which would gradually pave way to their employability. Many people, however, are very critical about higher education and think it is waste of time and money but in fact it is the way to earn money. However, "Technology is transforming work throughout the economy [13]." Technology is always associated with economy and it's the way of life.

Its only time invested money gained. If a particular piece of learning technology is no good, then it is to be identified. We as educators should look and guide students in a profitable way by thinking what is effective and what is not. On the other

hand potential is the opportunity to develop a much better understanding of the kinds of resources required for faculty to use technology in ways that consistently enhance student learning. "Many educators would agree that a vital indicator of student success is students' ability to develop both skills and an interest for lifelong learning [1]."

The relationship between higher education and the economy is longstanding. Employers generally see a student's achievements related to the subject discipline as necessary but not sufficient for them to be recruited. In some employment contexts, the actual subject discipline may be relatively unimportant. Achievements outside the boundaries of the discipline such as the possession of so-called 'soft skills' are generally considered to be important in the recruitment of graduates. 'Employability' refers to a graduate's achievements and their potential to obtain a suitable job, and should not be confused with the actual acquisition of a 'graduate job' which is subject to influences in the environment, a major influence being the state of the economy. "Employability derives from complex learning, and is a concept of wider range than those of 'core' and 'key' skills [13]." The flexibility of skills is often too easily assumed. There is some evidence to suggest that references to employability make the implicit assumption that graduates are young people. The risk is of not considering employability in respect of older graduates, who have the potential to bring a more extensive life.

A practically oral survey on the students have been carried around the campus as what would be their desire and interest once they would finish their course of study in their particular field. Amazingly the answers altogether were focused on the issues related as to how they would enter into the real world to earn name and fame for themselves by serving the community with their best ability to serve the humanity. This means a lot for them as it is the priority and they mean to survive with it and find a suitable employability that would be a real challenge for them in this competitive world.

Virtual Classrooms create wonderful, powerful and effective communicative learning environments. These programs integrate such features as whiteboard, chat, audio, video, questions and responses, PowerPoint slide shows and sharing of desk top applications. Online learners can even work in groups inside virtual rooms created by the instructor and then return to a common space to present their projects to the whole class. The entire class can also visit a group to watch their presentations on the group's whiteboard. "You can reuse your resources and learning objects. Technology will provide a means of feedback [5]."

We have to believe that effective use of technology has the potential to transform the student-teacher relationship at the undergraduate level. "Most teachers are eager to embrace new technologies, as they have seen their students' excitement and motivation increase when they do so. With technology standards becoming an integral part of students' education, teachers are more enthusiastic than ever to learn new technologies and methods [14]."

By using technology we will able to use the power of the person, who they are and what they are. The teacher's

inspirational role is going to become really much greater. "Having a wired classroom will have a wondering classroom, create a sense of value, putting students in charge, and teach tech terms [9]." Plans to continue integrating computer interaction with more traditional classroom activities will definitely allow students to observe a live classroom setting and will be most rewarding and challenging. In such case, the faculty members, like many others across the University, will continue to use technology to challenge both themselves and their students.

New technologies are enhancing our understanding of how students learn and providing instructors the ability to customize course materials and create personalized learning experiences tailored to students' individual needs. "Maintain creativity at local level. Create and foster an atmosphere of trust [7]." Students want to attend a university effectively integrate the latest technologies and teaching methods into their education. Innovative faculty are exploring new and interesting ways to integrate technology into their curriculum.

IV. CONCLUSION

Integrated practice of learning would definitely gain employment is true and practical. A clear phenomenal idea is that every teacher is a learner. And every teacher should take it to their heart, mind and soul to understand this phenomenon so that they would enrich the students mind with confidence and ideas for a better employment when they finish their course or study in universities. This new set of skills and its vast potential for collaboration offers new hope for an informed global society with a civic view of the goals of education. While therefore serving the prospects for democracy, this new reality complicates outmoded notions of individual achievement. "Achievement of success thus requires that faculty take the core of knowledge that is vital to us and integrate it with the new learning modes. Our new student learners are motivated to acquire information, but they have much to learn about what information to savor and how to use information and communication to various ends [10]." Thus, this paper would unanimously reinforce the learner and the teacher to a better prospect in life. A good teacher helps the learners to inherit the freedom of understanding and ability through which they not only stop with learning but move forward in the stairs of achievement by climbing a ladder of success in their life by being capable of employability.

Finally, this is the idea that students are not only meant to learn through technology but also earn through integrated practices that they have learnt and to incorporate their ability and understanding to create an opportunity for employment.

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